

Economic Challenges of COVID 19 in Developing Countries. (Case study Landlocked Countries)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

World over the assurance over developing countries in avoiding the worst of the worst Pandemic by the virtual of isolation. The epidemic has hit developing countries very hard underscoring the urgent need for renewed world action. No country has spared the pandemic result. Particular challenges in Landlocked countries and corruption, governance which factors of singular ill-equipped to deal with the pandemic crisis most of these countries need to withstand a COVID 19 precisely what many states lack.

A government with institutional capacity to deliver an action plan. Adequate security enforces rules, social programs, and care for infected people.

Keywords: ECONOMY, PANDEMIC CRISIS, LANDLOCKED AND DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

1. Introduction

Landlocked countries have immediate effects and are evident in public health, Many parts of African countries have few beds, and you find others having ventilators for the entire country. You find that many effective responses require government trust. Still, nations recover from conflict and corruption due to scarce capacity in that much lack of popular legitimacy. Many people will be unwilling to follow even that leading capability (Kaufman, 1997). In many private sectors with necessary productive countries, many will be able to work and support government must generate tax revenues to help those who couldn't while other economies through which to meet other people's needs. Increased incidences of the Pandemic in sub Saharan diseases will strain underfunded health care systems. Towards the end of March several African heads of state called for a U.S. \$100 billion stimulus package with calling for the suspension of debt service payments to help the continent¹ combat coronavirus for those attending meetings agreed repayment of both borrowed money to be considered. Covid-19 isn't only a medical emergency. It's also an upending social, economic life

¹ African heads of state called for a US \$100 billion stimulus package with calling for suspension of debt service payments to help the continent.

of many countries and its path. Worst of the economic effects on the Pandemic will surely fall not just of internal lockdowns, because of the overseas management. Business with many big countries like China has massively declined on revenue remittances tumbled plummeted on commodities with price and oil revenues with deficits in a balloon with relying on imports for much of their food which leads to increasing talk on hunger and famine. With all concepts, the poor will ever stay poor in years to come. The pandemic problems will escalate further, whereby developing countries problems will be world problems of terrorism and economic spillover.

Map 1 Africa's most affected areas with Covid-19

Source: Corona African map cases on the world map

In the early days of the crisis, many complex hopes that many nations escape the worst of a pandemic on health impact owing to their isolation with our perspective on new state councils with fragility, which wasn't the case (Hamblyn 1966). It has been proved beyond reasonable doubt; so many countries in Africa and the Asia Pacific have had infection and mortality rates on rival

pace in more developed countries that the Pandemic hit.²This has made a top priority to draw much attention to the unique challenges which have comprised former World leaders and heads of developing organizations in the combination of research with detailed policy knowledge to influence the global and national decision-makers who could be determined by fare nations through the crisis and tackling their border challenges³. Many decentralization, adaptability in insights which could prove critical nations but acting fast before the acute phase of the corona virus in west ends and the sense of agency. Social protection is made fast and simple with some timing that means universal eligibility rather than precise targeting internet connection, which is used to gather information and distribute small regular payments.

Domestic food production encouraged many countries to grow rice. Still, it has become increasingly dependent on imports over the last decade, on the most significant percentage of unused arable land on efforts to produce staple crops locally, which could be scaled up quickly and sustainably. The international community is looking at a vaccine available by more rich countries when the threat is a contagious pathogen. No country is safe unless encouraging and accelerating the production of multiple vaccines to ensure widespread distribution.

Business in developing countries needs direct support with the best financial institutions on small companies in poorer countries which are overlooked and tend to suffer from the perverse effects of broader targets and rules which precisely move enterprise that merit more excellent Investment. G20 countries need to give more support to heavily indebted nations that are being forced between paying creditors and saving their people this year alone. Moreover, essential that all nations secure emergency funding to support efforts to curb COVID-19 and impact on economic impact – including countries that are not ordinarily eligible for financing from the World Bank or the International Monetary Fund. Existing wounds worldwide due to COVID-19 with swift global action that could mitigate the Pandemic's worst effects will save livelihoods if we can move faster than the virus.

1.1 Statement problem

Most landlocked countries struggle a lot in trade term ethics when it undergoes policy arrangement which does not create wealth and achieve the improved gross domestic product. One of the perceived obstacles to achieving these is the death of landlocked capital countries. They are seen as a practical option and obstacle of trade-in fastening the pandemic shipments to help in cubing the disease in those countries; therefore, it's a nightmare in addressing a problem as it does in already established and developed countries. For example, a dependent school opposes the Pandemic in every country due to the political situations and management, giving an example of Tanzania Burundi and South Sudan and the losing their lives though less reported on the World Map. On the other hand, proponents of Investment argue that Investment is essential for any developing nation to achieve any measure of economic growth and development. Also, arguments occur in bringing a

² Many countries in Africa and the Asia Pacific have had infection and mortality

³ Influence the global and national decision-makers who could be determined by fare nations through the crisis and tackling their border challenges.

package of relatively cheap scarce capital, advanced technology, and superior technical knowledge to the home country. Several studies have already been done in the area, but this work is motivated towards a certain true position.

2. Literature review

2.1 Identify, disseminate, and evaluate promising innovations in real time.

Identify, disseminate, and evaluate promising innovations in real-time. The initiatives to identify innovations include the COVID-19 developed by many international development institutions. Many have featured deployable to inspirational change categorized across many areas and funding opportunities to help innovation find follow on funding (Hamblyn 1966). To facilitate the understanding, Covid-19 started to visualize data trends and welcomes partnerships to analyze and capture lessons learned about adapting scaling in response. Beyond in parallel to nations in economic cooperation and developments in all countries together with the European member state, tech companies, and civil society mobilized global crisis aftermath.

b. The digitalization in reaching scale during a pandemic.

The primary response of I.T. was dramatically demonstrated by keeping connected with others during lockdown with highly relevant for specific development areas, including schools and efforts to integrate digital learning during the crisis and beyond⁴. But its contribution by many bed nets to fight malaria in countries like Benin during the Pandemic with many working groups scale in agriculture in its call for increased rural internet access in social protection and support of crisis.

c. Different responses between developing countries and high-income economies.

Several researchers emphasize critical differences between high income and developing countries concerning the effects of the Pandemic and cost-effective with responses to it. Uganda's experience with the Ebola crisis may well be more pertinent for low-income countries than the skills of South Korea in responding Covid-19⁵. In the barriers and enabling factors, scale-up innovative approaches can be completely different in developing countries compared with high-income countries of differences in demographic characteristics of informality in the economy.

2.2 Recognize sector specificities.

Many contributions illustrate responses that can be tailored in specific in many circumstances with given examples. With health organizations fighting Covid-19, countries with the appropriate testing approach in applying lessons from the Ebola crisis in addressing the mobility and logistical constraints in maintaining health care chains of different nations, especially in agriculture and food security solutions that begin to emerge in assisting the rural poor. In education ministry, resources and strategies have emerged overnight to support children while out of school with remote education technologies and alternatives to school meals. So

⁴ Highly relevant for specific development areas, including schools and efforts to integrate digital learning during the crisis and beyond.

⁵The Ebola crisis may well be more pertinent for low-income countries than the skills of South Korea in responding Covid-19.

many innovative approaches are used to get children back to school as soon as possible while integrating learning remotely into the classrooms (Okedi, 1970). A number of the youth represent a primary demographic in many countries. At the same time, less susceptible to direct health effects on the virus is likely to be struck by the economic fallout from the crisis. Youth employment opportunities with particular importance for social and medium enterprises with heightened risks of survival in assisting them during and after the disaster and the role of women in communities deserve specific support.

b. Implementing organizations to adapt incentives with agencies.

Contributors stressed various areas where development agencies with programmatic flexibility and decentralized delivery system are likely to be better at adapting in response to mobility. The establishment of international agencies, e.g., IFAD, are adjusting their delivery modalities in higher amounts of financing and increasing the impact of support. Monitoring and planning evaluation radically transformed to meet social distancing and uncertainty.

2.3 Challenges to Land Locked Countries

Several landlocked countries count for 7% of the world population representing 15% of the United Nations membership, are the least economically integrated with the world. Landlocked countries are at the fringes of the world economy, accounting for only 0.9% of World gross output and 0.8% of global exports, which predicts high savings of heterogeneous both inter of level development and economic structure. Low developed countries' average per capita income is 2.5 higher than average. However, it masks the considerable dispersion amongst these countries ranging from \$271 to \$7925. Landlocked country's status relies heavily on seaports for international goods and services. Ordinarily, conditions face high trade costs than transit countries despite efforts to facilitate market access.

Graph 1 Share of landlocked countries

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators database.

Landlocked countries depend highly on exports while others rely on tourism as the primary source of foreign exchange earnings, making high vulnerable swings in external flows. Afghanistan, Central African Republic, Mali, and South Sudan are mired in protracted civil war and conflicts simultaneously. Burundi, Chad, Ethiopia, Nepal, Niger, and Uganda experienced violence, instability, and conflicts in recent years. Economic and political areas remain a challenge for many landlocked countries that may flare again should economic conditions and employment prospects⁶ deteriorate quickly in the period of Covid-19 has hit Europe and other developed countries the hardest Impacting on a reverberating in the far set of World corners including landlocked countries which spare the economic consequences of the Pandemic on country groups given a high degree of heterogeneity and macroeconomic transmission channels with significance in different countries.

2.4 Remoteness can be a blessing but not entirely

On confirmed cases, totaling 30,000 representing less percentage of all cases worldwide that remains relatively less affected by the virus, Afghanistan, Armenia, Kazakhstan, and the Republic of Moldova account for more than all COVID-19 cases in Landlocked countries. The statistics may well significantly underestimate the actual spread of infections due to limited capacities in reporting. Most of the landlocked countries introduced partial lockdowns. In contrast, others formally introduced a state of emergency Governments enforced a range of measures travel bans, educational institutions, public events, and social distancing. They are giving existing health conditions and limited general capacities with vulnerability to the Pandemic, mainly Landlocked African countries with large on compromised people. Many H.I.V. affected the population most likely to face toll deaths in 2017.

HIV/AIDS in such countries will likely result in high death tolls. It is most likely relatively remoteness of landlocked countries, which could offer them the degree of cushion against a large-scale outbreak. Most of these countries are geographically remote from countries barring a few landlocked countries in Europe hardest hit by the Pandemic. Having few direct flights between these countries in hardest-hit cities in Europe and the United States International tourist arrivals in the percentage of host country populations than lower for Landlocked country groups that limit the scope for other nationals spreading the virus Many countries are sparsely populated in the world which goes below 20 people in 10 landlocked countries compared to the global average of 60 percent people per square kilometer but surprising a few countries have lower numbers of people living per square kilometer among the least urbanized countries in the world as a percentage of the total population is less than 30% in landlocked countries compared to the global average of 55%.

The economic structure may also explain the relatively few cases in Landlocked countries in manufacturing activities accounts for less than expected percentage of G.D.P. making them the least intensive economies in the world and service sector activities which mean less physical proximity and less scope for a symptom transmission of the virus Less concentration, physical remoteness and economic activities of

⁶ Economic and political areas remain a challenge for many landlocked countries that may flare again should economic conditions and employment prospects.

urbanization which provide some protection against the spread of the virus in that many Landlocked countries are vulnerable Lao Nepal, Republic of Moldova and Tajikistan, among others as sizeable fares of their populations live and work abroad are often compelled to live congested in squalid quarters in the host country many of them have been returning to their homelands in the past couple of months. More significant outbreaks in these landlocked countries remain a distinct possibility.

Graph 2. Remoteness compulsion on Trade

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators database.

2.5 Collapsing commodity prices a challenge for macroeconomic stability

World Economic prospects of 2020 trade are forecast to contract by 15% amid sharply reduced global demand and disruptions worldwide supply chain. Most Landlocked countries' trade sector remains the main driver of export and fiscal revenue and economic growth depending on exporting one primary commodity. The Agricultural sector in landlocked countries for a significant percentage of G.D.P., over 80% of the budget⁷ revenue and Coffee exports comprise of dealing with neighboring countries with dependent already battered by the collapse in prices. The sharp slowdown in growth in China has led to a decline of around 30% in natural products from central Asia. In Latin America (Graham 1927-1928), some countries are highly dependent on exports of natural resources. The current crisis takes the score with the need for economic diversification from during problems with additional constraints with Investment and trade.

2.5.1 Legality much as the landlocked country is examined by the Pandemic

Result in most countries of the world, are subject to restrictions and regulations. In some countries, licensed

⁷ The Agricultural sector in landlocked countries for a significant percentage of GDP over 80% of the budget.

and could work hand in hand to protect the territories under the communities like East African Community ECOWAS, etc., through three main ways direct trade. This is done through the seller and posts an offer, and the website alerts when a buyer wants to trade (Maloumy-baka & Kingombe, 2016). In trade, the seller and buyer have to actively engage in negotiation and fulfill the transaction if a deal is agreed upon exchange trades.

2.5.2 Landlocked Countries and Digital currency

Scams, just like with fiat money, is referred to as fake currency because most people don't know the genuinely used currency and its value to the economy, which makes many easily be conned a number of them when they trade into a scam it's challenging to convince the trader on how he has been conned (Bajo-Rubio, 2000). Under commission agents due to pyramid setups whereby investors are promised high returns based on the aggressiveness of recruiting new traders and the currency is centralized, and selling is controlled effect clones of a parent website while genuine are decentralized. This is a big issue for Somalia in particular, but in many other Landlocked countries, MoneyGram that in S.S.A. control 2/3 of the market, are unchallenged, and free to impose their own –usually high –prices (Aggawal, G, 2006). Furthermore, some African put in more exclusivity arrangements that limit the institutions authorized to offer remittance. Other causes of the high prices of remittances include exclusive partnerships between banks and M.T.O., although initiatives in recent years to end these agreements. Also, the anti–money laundering and combating the financing of terrorism (AML-CFT) regulations have contributed to this. However, there have been initiatives in recent years to simplify AML-CFT rules for low-value transfers.

2.3 Causes of the high transaction costs of remittances to and within Africa

Transaction costs are high in most African countries due to underdeveloped financial and payment infrastructures in rural areas, which contributes to keeping remittance costs so high since money sent and received may not circulate easily, making inefficient remittance services(Graham, n.d.). Inadequate remittance services result in social costs for remittance senders and receivers, as the former may not have easy access to remittance service providers, and the latter may not be able to collect the funds transferred promptly. This relates to the underdeveloped financial system in Africa, as witnessed by its under-banking. The consequence of this will be the limited use of financial services, which contributes to increasing remittance. Such underuse of the existing formal economic infrastructures will result in a lack of transparency in the market and a lack of competition.

The transparency issue is related to whether the remittance sender is sufficiently and correctly informed on all the components of the total transaction cost (direct fee charged, exchange rate applied and any tax charged to him, on the one hand, and possible fees charged to the receiver, on the other hand) and on the speed of the transaction service(Graf Von Der Schulenburg et al., 2008). The lack of transparency by agents is the most important factor explaining high remittance prices because it gives no chance to remitters to compare. It must be argued that, although lifting or eliminating exclusivity clauses open the market's competition, as it happened in Morocco and Senegal, the remittance price reduction will not depend solely on such a Way forward for

currency important that some countries are now considering retiring their fiat currencies to introduce national digital currency (Arcand, 2013).

Proposed Methodology

The study employs two approaches to assess the viability of including Bitcoin in the international reserves portfolio of the Central Bank of Barbados. The first approach is a counterfactual simulation where it is assumed that a fixed proportion of the Central Bank's portfolio of foreign currency balances was invested in Bitcoin (Aggawal, G, 2006). The actual exchange rate changes are then applied to the portfolio to compare the simulated relative to the actual outcome. This assessment provides an assessment of the potential differences in volatility and returns resulting from investments⁸. Relatively small investment ratios of 0.01, 0.1, and 1 percent are considered, and for comparison purposes, a scenario where 5 percent of the reserves are invested in Bitcoin is also considered. In the second approach, Monte Carlo methods investigate the effects of randomly generated shocks on developing countries' portfolios of international assets over various forecasted time horizons (2015-2025)(Schulenburg et al., 2008). The likelihood that the stock of international reserve assets is exhausted in a given year of the simulation period is then calculated over 5000 model iterations. At the end of each period, international reserves are influenced by demand-side shocks and exchange rates.

3.1 Cryptocurrencies as Part of the International Reserves

Counterfactual simulations were done over the period 2009 to present suggest that adding Bitcoin to the reserve portfolio of the central bank would not significantly increase volatility but could provide opportunities to offset exchange rate depreciation against major currencies such as the Pound and the Euro. Data Description and Proposed Methodology the proposed study comprises the data of developing and emerging countries for the period of 2000 to 2015 (Hurlburt & Bojanova, 2014). Percentage of net Crypto Currency and the dependent variable and the data of prescribed variables are discovered by world development indicators World Bank have been taken from World Development Indicators. Data of terrorism activities will be taken from World Bank), the capital flight data will be calculated by using one coin analysis constant⁹, as 100% of the transaction when accepting bitcoins, unlike using credit cards done by for the case of 37 African developing countries(Blundell, 2014). Total investments are calculated by taking the first gross fixed capital formation difference. The data of other economic indicators will be calculated from I.M.F.'s balance of payment statistics, the direction of trade statistics, international financial statistics (I.F.S.), the World Bank development indicators (W.D.I.), and global development finance(Bank, 2012).

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reserve portfolio of the central bank would not significantly increase volatility but could provide opportunities to offset exchange rate depreciation against 14 major currencies such as the Pound and the Euro (Davis, 2011). The figures assume that some fixed amount of reserves is held in balances denominated in a particular currency at the beginning¹⁰ of the period and held for the remainder. They are therefore only affected by the exchange rate.

4. Theoretical Model

As for the observations, we could use some approaches, Monte Carlo methods, to investigate the effects of randomly generated shocks on Developing countries' portfolios of international assets over various forecasted time horizons (Hurlburt & Bojanova, 2014). The likelihood that the stock of global reserve assets is exhausted in a given year of the simulation period is then calculated over 5000 model iterations. At the end of each period, international reserves are influenced by demand-side shocks, exchange rate shocks, and the initial stock of international reserves. In each year of the simulation, the projected demand for imports and international payments¹¹ is set equal to the last period's accounts, plus randomly generated payments and exchange rate shocks. These shocks' mean and standard deviation are set equal to their historical value for the period (Moore & Christin, 2013). The steps in the simulation are set to one month, and a single run is performed for 1-, 2-, 5- and 10-year horizons. The analysis is then replicated 5,000 times, and summary statistics are presented. Methodology

In the basis specified system, the equation on Landlocked countries is checked by variables in the method. Pre and post elevens are conducted to check agriculture incidents in the country.

$$I_t = \alpha + \beta T_t + \delta I_{t-1} + \varphi_1 IN_t + \varphi_2 Y_t + \varphi_3 i_t + \varphi_4 Ex_t + \varphi_5 E_t + \varphi_6 TO_t + \varphi_7 IC_t + \varphi_8 LLCs_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The stand on Landlocked countries added the first GFCF. "Y" is G.D.P., "i" is the inflation rate and "Ex" is

¹⁰ The figures assume that some fixed amount of reserves are held in balances denominated in a particular currency at the beginning

¹¹ In each year of the simulation, the projected demand for imports and international payments.

the exchange rate; that captures expected Investment. "E" is education results with Investment because multinational firms need to prefer operation in countries with low literacy, while multinational firms also require a highly skilled labor force, and they choose a country with a high literacy rate. "TO" is trade openness, as assumed that open economies are better and favorable for export oriented Investment. "I.C." and "L.L.C.s" represent the internal conflict and landlocked countries. In the second model, L.L.C.s and Capital flight dependent variable, with another factor as control variables, as it has been presented in Equations 2 and 3. In these mentioned models, E.C. refers to External conflict, and M is the infrastructure expenditure incurred for public transport safety¹². At the same time, T opens the housing activities, including domestic, transnational, and total.

$$LLCs_t = \alpha + \beta T_t + \delta I_{t-1} + \varphi_1 M_t + \varphi_2 Y_t + \varphi_3 i_t + \varphi_4 Ex_t + \varphi_5 E_t + \varphi_6 TO_t + \varphi_7 IC_t + \varphi_8 EC_t + \varepsilon_t$$

(Eq. 2)

$$CAP_t = \alpha + \beta T_t + \delta I_{t-1} + \varphi_1 M_t + \varphi_2 Y_t + \varphi_3 i_t + \varphi_4 Ex_t + \varphi_5 E_t + \varphi_6 TO_t + \varphi_7 IC_t + \varphi_8 LLCs_t + \varepsilon_t$$

(Eq. 3)

$$CAP_{it} = \alpha + \beta T_{it} + \delta I_{t-1} + \varphi_1 M_{it} + \varphi_2 Y_{it} + \varphi_3 i_{it} + \varphi_4 Ex_{it} + \varphi_5 E_{it} + \varphi_6 TO_{it} + \varphi_7 IC_{it} + \varphi_8 LLCs_{it} + \varepsilon_t$$

4.1 Research Gap

An emerging digital instrument is increasingly being referred to as even cheaper than cell phones. That is, without the need of banks or any other financial intermediary in an entirely decentralized way, transfer fees will be significantly lower (Moore & Christin, 2013). These users and volunteer developers keep track of transactions and update the records of transactions in real time. It is worth highlighting that no single user, company, or central authority keeps track of such transactions and updates their records. "The records of all confirmed transactions are then kept on a shared public ledger — that is, a big publicly available spreadsheet — known as the currencies impossible to tamper.

The blockchain doesn't work without Bitcoin within developed, underdeveloped, and landlocked countries. They are the same thing. Build applications on top of that technology but not take Bitcoin away. However, venture investors are increasingly talking about the value of this distributed ledger system as a basis for all kinds of applications, not just currency. The blockchain, whose performance and integrity are enforced with Cryptography to ensure validation of transactions, allows Bitcoin wallets to know their balance and make new trades by the spender (Bank, 2012). It could reduce the cost and increase the speed and accuracy of financial transactions; it could genuinely disrupt the banking business. Choking off terrorists' finances, and tensions between established and upstart financial institutions and between regulatory agencies". For diaspora communities that provide critical aid and capital flows to Landlocked countries, the distributed ledger technology can reduce the time and costs to send money overseas.

¹² In these below mentioned models EC refers External conflict and M is expenditure incurred for public Transport.

Graph 3 Reserves in Landlocked countries most affected by Pandemic

Counter Factual simulation with different portfolio holdings in One coin

Source: Authors' Calculations

As the ratio increases, the end of period balance diverges significantly. With just 0.1 percent of reserves in central Banks, balances would have been more than twice the actual amount, 19 times greater with 1 percent of funds and some 100 times more significant with a relatively sizeable 5 percent of reserves in one coin. The potential returns on these balances can also be quite significant. If historical values of the mean and standard deviation are used for the simulation, the portfolio value rises from just \$27,000 in May 2015 to \$224 million by the end of 2025. These projections obviously have a large margin of error given the long forecast horizon being considered. In addition, using historical performance is not always a good gauge of future returns for financial assets.

4.2 Impacts of COVID-19 on G.D.P. in Landlocked countries

The agricultural sector is dominant in most landlocked economies. 3.7 percent over 90-99 compared to the far more impressive growth of the industrial and service sectors, the importance of agriculture in these economies with 82 percent of the workforce, accounts for 90 percent of export earnings¹³, and provided 44 percent of G.D.P. Moreover, most farmers in Landlocked countries, like 2.5 million smallholdings and scattered large farms, provide staple food requirements. Most countries can stay on agriculture due to the country's excellent access to waterways, fertile soils, and Agricultural produce into crops, and horticultural produce and coffee, tea, cotton, tobacco, and cocoa.¹⁴

. Increasingly excluded from the economy and unable to lower transaction costs and remain competitive.

4.3 Domestic policy

Incentives on women to spend time attending on farms on which food is based, instead gain employment in the export sector. The effect of policies is to burden women with the added responsibility of providing food for the household. It is taken for granted women will provide in the reproductive economy. Farmers who

¹³(I) a declining share of GDP and employment;

(ii) rural urban movement stimulates urbanization; (iii) the rise of modern industrial and service economy

¹⁴(ii) rural urban that stimulates urbanization; (iii) the rise of modern industrial

compete in this environment tend to look for the land, and women are increasingly excluded from the economy. Unable to lower transaction costs and remain on food grown for consumption.

4.3.1 Commercialization Impact

Economic household food production, social activities, education, and leisure. (Okedi, 1970) 's the source of family income may even decline in real terms, further lowering her bargaining potential within the household¹⁵. In the main areas, women farmers inactive with non traditional agricultural exports with export promotion and to take advantage of positive effects – of trade expansion Country

4.3.2 Landlocked countries on Economic Success

The main program in policy investment, privatization of public enterprises. This resulted in rapid G.D.P. growth, domestic market, and supply of goods to increase exports. However, despite the success, there has been a lack of clarity on the full impact of SAP policies on the sustainability of fisheries resources.

4.4 The primary food crops from landlocked countries

Mainly domestic consumption includes plantations, cassava, maize, millet, and sorghum. Although production is apparent in some areas, this is normally a mixture known as "agro-pastoralists" (integrated cattle and crop farming). It should be noted that pastoralists decline due to the constant cattle raids by southern Sudan and counter parts and aid agencies in an intervention that encourages the fencing to land and discourage the traditional free-roaming of cattle. The analysis of the developments is then disaggregated spatially, showing geographic differences as well as commonalities¹⁶ Spatial analysis further moves assess the extent of diversification and specialization of Ugandan farmers and factors behind the decisions to diversify and commercialize, farms and discusses pros and cons of supporting certain farm models for commercialization Continuation in important role in Ugandan economy, but its share has significantly declined over time. The declining share of the economy is not necessarily a bad thing if rural-urban migration stimulates manufacturing and services¹⁷. But in most Landlocked countries, Transformation happened in recent two decades, The manufacturing remained at the low percent of G.D.P., while the agriculture is still at around 70 percent

Chapter 5: Reasons to believe in growth in landlocked countries

Uganda has that smallholder agriculture is likely to perform much better than believed greatly diversified its export. Landlocked countries are the largest source of locally-procured maize in Africa. Farmers will keep having diversified until they get adequate access and factors of production to disconnect their production decisions from and consumption.

5.1 Impede growth on structural constraints

Potential strained by the aging equipment in the production side economy, access to different sectors becomes limited and financing. The government's inability to secure ongoing assistance in the country's economic

¹⁵The agricultural panel surveys expected by the end of 2010 will allow better addressing these of these inconsistencies. Over the long period for example, only USAID spent nearly much time on such programs.

¹⁶ Showing differences with in commonalities.

¹⁷ The declining share of the economy is not necessarily a bad thing if rural migration stimulates services.

programs with problematic settlement in fiscal space on operational commitments in the community. Mounting imbalances with rigid compound demands taking 1–3%, on risk management process with landlocked countries Business Policies

Business viewed an important stimulus growth and policies which contribute on poverty within landlocked countries contribute to Landlocked countries to poverty effort reduction within the last 16 years, Business policy results pursued through continued with increased involvement on all sectors consisting of Uganda, Kenya and the United Republic of Tanzania and COMESA Contract farming, smallholders and commercialization of agriculture in Uganda. Study under the UPTOP Business Research Fund.

. Arrangements involved inter-governmental authority for development that aims to foster economic cooperation with member states signatory to the records countries preferential business and links with European Union. Difficulties in drafting notification by various agreements with relevancy to agriculture business

5.2 Enterprise Role in Landlocked Countries

Governments established bodies in different departments to ensure that farmers and exporters maintain quality of products to provide backstopping which continued with the privatization program. Almost three-quarters of all public enterprises have either been slated for divestiture had been sold on companies, and the most recent privatization carried out liquidity and telecommunication. Many privatization sectors continue experiencing banking services and electricity. Government anticipation on privation completed in the transportation and sectors with many priorities are the reforms and development of more effective and timely reforms.

5.3 Contribution of Chinese companies on Fishing in some landlocked countries

According to different experts, resource endowment of Landlocked countries with a significant percentage on fisheries and aquaculture production like Uganda's fisheries includes the five large lakes, including Lake Victoria 160 minor swamps and floodplains, all of which are habitats fish suitable sites for fish farming. On (FOCAC) is helping East Africa boost fish farming industry, The Asian country under the eight measures announced by the leading has set up a five million U.S. dollar. At the center, located on the outskirts of the capital Kampala, local farmers are trained in modern ways of fish farming using simple and affordable technologies and the provision of fish hatcheries. Fish experts from across the East African region also visit the center to share knowledge on best practices of fish farming. They have also introduced Chinese fish species that can do well in Uganda's environment. the fisheries sub sector is estimated to contribute 12 percent to the agricultural G.D.P. and 2.5 percent to the national G.D.P. Fish emerged as a non-traditional export commodity in the late 1980s, with export earnings increasing from 5.3 million U.S. dollars in 1991 to 83.3 million dollars in 2010. The primary export market is the European Union and others, including the Middle East, United States, Egypt, and Southeast Asia. In addition to international exports, there is a dramatic increase in regional export markets to neighboring countries like the Democratic Republic of Congo and South Sudan. Statistics from the department of fisheries indicated Uganda produces 450,000 tons of fish out of the required 650,000 tons.

The Chinese company Huaqiao Fenghuang Group running the demonstration center in conjunction with the Ugandan government, has submitted its investment plan to the government. If approved by the government, the over 172 million dollar investment plan will come into force in 2014 at the end of the three-year project by the Chinese government. Under its local name Uganda Huaqiao Fenghuang Fisheries Co. Lt, the company will set up a fish feed factory to produce 200,000 tons per annum. According to the proposal, they also plan to set up a fish processing factory with a capacity to produce 20,000 tons of fish products per annum. Besides pond farming, several areas on Ugandan lakes are being mapped out for the designation of cage farming. The designated areas will be leased out to investors to increase fish production and the creation of employment.

Conclusion and policy implications

The combination of escalating disruptions and the slow and uneven response to the COVID-19 outbreak contributes to political crises in several of the largest economies. South African president, during an address to the nation on Sunday, labeled the crisis as a warning that impacts businesses and jobs in South Africa. Senegalese president for all schools to be closed for the next three weeks and for all religious festivals to be canceled. His government is also working with a U.K. firm on a hand-held coronavirus test. However, the paper notes that as the proportion of reserves held in the rising situation, the volatility of reserves would also increase. Generally, the result of this study suggests that increasing adoption of Bitcoin and ripples under currencies can influence income generation in the young generation through central Banks research should have paid attention and addressed the research. Moreover, it will be better if future research works study the problem using panel data analysis.

The only trade policy identified in this regard was measured promoting higher value addition of exports. The country studies also suggest that integrated treatment of policies underpinning economic development may enhance the viability of policies directed towards the environmental and social aspects of sustainable development in these countries. The procedures to be considered should include not only macroeconomic balance and stability but also pay due attention to infrastructure and incentive structures for development. For example, devaluation will need to be balanced with higher value added for which incentives such as tax rebates would be required. In addition, improved infrastructure would be needed to build a competitive export structure. In several cases, commodity price stabilization, skewed preferential trade agreements, and other such factors may also need to be corrected before the right balance between trade, environment, and development can be achieved. It is hoped that the stakeholder buy-in generated during the process of the assessment will help some of the countries to begin this work soon. Outputs from these assessments have already been used in the Development of the UNCTAD Train for Trade course on trade, environment, and development. They can also serve as valuable models for countries involved in similar exercises in the UNEP-UNCTAD Capacity Building Task Force on Trade, Environment, and Development (CBTF) framework. This task force is already providing capacity building for environmental and integrated

assessment of trade-related policies and designing appropriate policy responses to such reviews.

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